

VALUE4FARM

DELIVERABLE D6.1 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

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Nature of the Deliverable

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level

PU	Public, fully open and automatically posted online	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grand Agreement	
CI	Classified information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
	Classified information: CONFIDENTIAL UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AU – Aarhus Universitët
CIB – Consorzio Italiano Biogas e Gassificazione
DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DST – Decision Support Tool
EIHP – Energetski Institut Hrvoje Pozar
EQY – Euroquality
INA – INAGRO
IP(R) - Intellectual Property (Rights)
IUNG – Instytut Uprawy Nawożenia I Gleboznawstwa, Panstwowy Instytut Badawczy
KPI – Key Performance Indicator
MRL – Market Readiness Level
PR – Project Result
SRL – Societal Readiness Level
TRL – Technology Readiness Level
UCSC – Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
UREAD – University of Reading
V4F – VALUE4FARM
WBA – World Biogas Association

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Value4Farm (V4F) project, launched in September 2023 with the Kick-Off meeting of all 14 consortium partners held in Brussels on 12-13 October 2023, aims to support the defossilisation and energy-independence of agriculture in Europe by demonstrating the feasibility, sustainability and effectiveness of coupling food production with green energy production systems on three demonstration farms in Belgium, Denmark and Italy – and the replicability of those value chains in three sites in Iceland, Italy and Poland.

The consortium brings together academics from leading European universities, trade associations and small businesses with expertise in the field of bioenergy, solar, agrivoltaics and biogas at the core of the renewable energy-generation technologies to be applied on those sites – with the ultimate objective of promoting circularity in the production of food as well as the generation of heat, electricity and fuel in the agriculture sector.

This Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan is the first deliverable of Work Package 6 (WP6) - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, led by the World Biogas Association (WBA) in partnership with EuroQuality (EQY) and implemented by all partners over the 42 months duration of the project. The key objective of WP6 is to coordinate and align project partners' dissemination, exploitation and communication efforts to maximise the impact of the V4F and the broad exploitation of its results in agriculture across Europe.

The DEC plan establishes the key responsibilities of each partner within the deployment of WP6 and provides a framework of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities to ensure its success. It lays out the strategy, audiences and tactics to raise awareness of and inform about the project, share the Project Results (PRs) with key stakeholders and support the effective uptake of the solutions within the farming community.

The plan maps out the dissemination, exploitation and communication networks available to WP6 among the consortium partners and identifies potential barriers and remedial action that needs to be taken to achieve the plans objectives. It also sets Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure success and provides a detailed implementation schedule to assist partners in delivering DEC activities over the duration of the project.

The plan is a living document that will be continuously updated as the project progresses, with formal reviews and updates to be published at M18 (February 2025) and M36 (August 2026).

Strategy, key audiences and message

To secure maximum impact of the V4F project, the key overarching strategy underpinning the DEC plan is to create a favourable environment for the deployment of the V4F results – in particular, in ensuring awareness and engagement of farmers, technology providers, researchers and policy makers in the work of the consortium from the outset, alongside investors and the broader public. The core message for all partners will be to promote the benefits of deploying V4F results as a way of creating sustainable and effective circular value chains in agriculture that couple food production with green energy production on farms.

Methodology/Tactics

The key elements supporting the delivery of the DEC plan are as follows:

- Technology providers/End-users advisory boards

To make sure that key target audiences are engaged with and advise on progress and feasibility of the project solutions, WBA will be setting up two advisory boards of between 10 and 20 members, bringing together technology providers, start-ups, industry organisations and scientists with expertise in bioenergy, solar, agrivoltaics, photovoltaics and biogas on one hand, and farmers, advisers, policy-makers, investors and other relevant stakeholders on the other. The Technology Providers Advisory Board and End-Users Advisory Board will be established over the first 12 months of the project and members will be invited to participate in regular online/physical meetings as well as visits to the demonstration and replication sites and the V4F final workshop organised by WBA.

- Sharing knowledge and networking opportunities

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are supported by the development of a database of relevant stakeholders and the mapping of existing relationships and networks, including other Horizon Europe and research projects, within each partner organisation. Alongside the Advisory Boards, this database will enable WBA and consortium partners to facilitate knowledge sharing and networking opportunities to support the development and deployment of the V4F project results, as well as create synergies between projects. This will be delivered through activities such as webinars and joint events.

- Communication / dissemination tools and activities
 - *Online platforms*

To support the DEC activities, having developed the V4F brand, EQY has launched the V4F website (www.Value4Farm.eu) and set-up X (formerly known as Twitter) and LinkedIn as online platforms to promote the work of the V4F project. EQY have already started running social media campaigns to raise awareness of the V4F project among the general public.

- *Promotional assets*

EQY has produced a range of materials that can be used by partners both digitally and as printed assets such as posters, presentation templates and pull-up banners. These are made available to partners on a SharePoint platform, set up by INAGRO, which also provides partners with all the reference documentation relevant to the project.

- *Newsletters/press releases*

EQY and WBA will be working together with partners to issue newsletters and press releases communicating the project progress and results on a regular basis and aimed at the largest possible audience. A press release introducing the project and announcing the Kick-off meeting has already been issued, translated into multiple languages and shared with partners for dissemination via their own networks.

- *Events*

Partners will both host and attend events (trade fairs, symposiums, conferences, workshops) to present the V4F project results and renewable energy technologies to relevant audiences. A preliminary list of events at which V4F could be featured has been developed in collaboration with all consortium partners and will continue to be reviewed to establish the best opportunities available to promote V4F and disseminate its results and messages. Already confirmed as events where V4F will be presented in 2024 are the World Biogas Expo (WBA) in July and Ecomondo (WBA/CIB) in November. WBA will also present V4F at their National Association Roundtable held in the Autumn. A detailed list is provided in Annex 1.

- *Scientific publications and articles*

Academic partners UFZ, AU, IUNG, EIHP, UCSC as well as REM and CIB will publish a minimum of 12 scientific papers relating to the project and support the production of more accessible articles to be placed in trade and mainstream media. WBA will work with partners to build a database of media outlets and journalists with whom to engage to raise broader awareness of the project.

- *Site visits*

AU, INA, REM, CIB and UCSC will work with WBA in organising visits to the demonstration sites in Denmark, Belgium and Italy for key stakeholders as well as the Technology Providers and End-Users Advisory Boards. Similar visits will be held in the replication sites in Iceland, Italy and Poland later in the project.

- Exploitation measures and strategies for market uptake of V4F PRs

The present deliverable includes specific exploitation measures for each of the PRs, providing first elements to the exploitation plan and ensuring the future uptake of the V4F Project Results:

- PR 1: Sustainable agricultural crop protocol for the Atlantic pedoclimatic region
- PR 2: Sustainable agricultural crop protocol for the Mediterranean pedoclimatic region
- PR 3: Protocol of good practices for handling already existing residual crop streams and usage of digestate
- PR 4: High-efficiency flameless microturbines
- PR 5: Path for maximising food and energy output for large-scale farms
- PR 6: Simple path to mobility for small-scale farms
- PR 7: Efficient off-grid biomethane plant
- PR 8: Open-access decision support tool

- Roadmap to higher TRL, MRL and SRL

Involving full engagement from all partners, the creation of a roadmap to higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), Market Level Readiness (MRL) and Societal Readiness Level (SRL) will be a key element of the exploitation activities, derived from the knowledge sharing and advisory boards engagement to pave the way to the uptake of the solutions in the different sectors. This DEC plan features an exploitation table for each of the eight PRs, providing a pathway towards impact of the outcomes and demonstrating the benefits of the V4F project value chains.

- Training

WBA, in collaboration with demonstration and replication partners, will organise between 15 and 20 training courses for farmers based on VAF outputs, notably protocols and the Decision Support Tool, with a focus on adapting the solutions to local needs. The aim is to gather a minimum of 6 farmers / session to ensure impact and facilitate successful uptake of the V4F solutions.

Barriers to implementation and mitigation

Consortium partners have identified barriers to the successful deployment of the V4F and identified mitigation measures around the following aspects:

Barriers	Mitigation
<u>Regional languages</u> – Ten languages are represented within the consortium.	External communications will be translated into local languages to ensure full understanding by the targeted audiences. This will include the V4F website.
<u>Technical language</u> – the project covers technical aspects which might be difficult for non-specialist audiences to understand	Communications will endeavour to avoid technical jargon and keep the language as accessible as possible – testing with end users if necessary.
<u>Political climate</u> – protests by farmers across Europe over the cost of implementing Green Deal measures and the overall financial viability of farming	Partners will actively interact with policy makers to promote the benefits of the V4F solutions and ensure that the transition is supported by EU and national governments (e.g. through financial incentives).
<u>Economic context</u> – the high investment needed to implement the transition to green technologies might impact on end-users' readiness to take up the V4F solutions.	Using detailed economic assessments and business cases from other WPs, WP6 will present the medium- and long-term economic benefits of embracing V4F outcomes throughout dissemination activities to facilitate exploitation.
<u>Societal context</u> – farmers might lack confidence in the value chains developed by V4F.	Farmers will be involved throughout the project through partners' networks, the End-Users Board and targeted dissemination.

<u>Legislative context</u> - lack of legislations/regulations and guidelines or national differences might discourage farmers from effectively implementing renewable energy technologies on their farms.	Dissemination activities will focus on engaging with policymakers whilst WP1 and WP4 will monitor the regulatory frameworks to ensure appropriate guidance is provided to farmers towards implementation of the solutions.
<u>Practical barriers to V4F activities</u> – funding, health and safety at sites, lack of engagement from key stakeholders, commitments	Good planning, H&S briefings, direct support from all partners, terms of reference for Advisory Board members and reviews of the DEC plan should help anticipate issues and avoid disruption in the roll out of the project.

Key Performance Indicators

Specific targets have been set across all main DEC activities with Poor/Good/Excellent Impact ratings to help monitor success and revise the DEC plan according to performance.

Implementation schedule

A schedule of delivery for each partner across the range of dissemination, exploitation and communications activities is provided as Annex 3 to assist with the effective deployment of WP6 over the duration of the V4F project.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND

The aim of Work Package 6 (WP6) is to coordinate and align project partners for strategic dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) efforts in order to maximise the impact of the Value4Farm (V4F) project. All partners are engaged in DEC activities, led by the World Biogas Association (WBA), with the communication activities led by Euroquality (EQY) – this plan will therefore set out the responsibilities of each partner in the delivery of WP6 activities.

The three areas of activities have been defined as follows:

- Dissemination: sharing the results of the project to the target stakeholders
- Exploitation: encouraging the take-up of the solutions
- Communication: raising awareness and informing on project progress

However, there will inevitably be overlap/duplication in implementation activities, which this plan seeks to minimise.

1.2. OBJECTIVE

The objective of Deliverable 6.1 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan is to set out the strategy, tactics and tools to support partners in the communication, dissemination and exploitation of the V4F project results and encourage the uptake of the value chain solutions towards decarbonisation and energy resilience of farming offered as an outcome of the project. The Plan represents a reference document for all partners to deliver on their WP6 engagement activities – defining target audiences and main messages, identifying dissemination, exploitation and communication goals and tools; establishing key performance indicators (KPIs); assessing barriers to implementation and mitigation strategy – as well as a providing detailed schedule of delivery for the duration of the project.

The plan also points to partner network and stakeholder analyses, stakeholder mapping and a database of stakeholders to be used by different project partners for their engagement activities. It is a living document which will be reviewed in the course of the project and updated at M18 (Feb 2025) and M42 (Feb 2027).

1.3. STRATEGY

Under the leadership of WBA, all partners will be involved in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities through dedicated tasks (T6.2: T6.3: T6.4) to maximise the potential of the project pathways towards widespread deployment of the project results (PRs). With a special focus on and engagement with farmers, the aim is to create a favourable environment for the development of agricultural protocols and energy solutions to support farmers with the defossilisation of the agricultural sector. This first action plan establishes the framework for delivery of these activities by each partner and the rules of engagement with the project's

audiences. It will be shared with all partners, with delivery of tasks and achievement of KPIs monitored and reviewed to ensure successful delivery of WP6, according to emerging communication, dissemination or exploitation needs from partners and/or update in strategy for communication, dissemination or exploitation activities.

2. AUDIENCES & MESSAGES

The overall message of the V4F project across all audiences, and in particular the general public, will be to promote the environmental and economic benefits of implementing sustainable value chains and utilising green energy technologies in the agricultural sector. Specific audience groups and messages have been also identified for targeted deployment as part of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities, as follows.

2.1 TARGET GROUP 1: FARMING COMMUNITY

Considering its objective to defossilise agriculture, the V4F project main audience is the farming community, represented through farmers and farmer organisations. A specific focus will be cast on farmers as the main beneficiaries of the value chains and solutions proposed by V4F. They will be encouraged to take up and deploy those solutions, as well as be invited to participate in the research process and to help gain access to the targeted market, which they can ease. The key messages for farmers will be centered around the benefits of generating green energy on their farm to meet their own demand, which enables them to achieve greater energy independence, save money, diversify their income and reduce their carbon footprint.

2.2 TARGET GROUP 2: TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS

Energy technology providers are identified as a relevant target group for V4F, especially from the fields of vertical and horizontal agrivoltaism, green biorefinery, microturbines, biogas compressor and tractor, anaerobic digestion and biogas upgrading (including biomethanation). Their interest will mainly lie in the development of microturbines for electricity production (PR4), and the demonstration of the technologies integrated to their regional value chain (PR5; path for maximising food and energy output for large-scale farms; PR6: simple path to mobility for small-scale farms; PR7: efficient off-grid biomethane plant). The key message to technology providers in the course of the project will be to engage in the research through participation in the board and in supporting the deployment of the technologies demonstrated by V4F.

2.3 TARGET GROUP 3: R&D COMMUNITY

Innovation in energy solutions and the tailored Decision Support Tool (DST) will be of interest for research groups and scientific communities in these fields. The scientific community will be targeted to foster research and enhance the technologies and value chains further. The key message to the R&D community is that V4F will bring an extensive scientific advance in the energy field and agricultural sector, and they need to be part of it.

2.4 TARGET GROUP 4: POLICY MAKERS AND PUBLIC BODIES

V4F's results concerning the achieved performance, the cost (Techno Economic Assessment), the environmental benefits (Life Cycle Analysis), and the societal acceptance (S-LCA and comprehensive social acceptance) will be disseminated to relevant policy makers to increase their awareness of the value chains and technologies as part of possible solutions for the future. Particularly, local policymakers will be targeted to raise their awareness of local solutions to produce decentralised renewable energy, and connect the relevant actors in order to implement the value chains. This will enable them to see the benefits of such renewable energy technologies for the agricultural sector. It is expected that policy makers will push for solutions enabling better legislation, which is strategic for the future of sustainable and circular agriculture and climate. This can be done through, for example, financing other projects, developing incentives, establishing regulations and further promoting adoption by relevant farmers.

2.5 TARGET GROUP 5: INVESTORS

Investors will be targeted by V4F for supporting the next phases of development and market introduction of the developed solutions, and for facilitating the uptake of the V4F solutions. The investing value for stakeholders will focus on the performance and advantages of the technologies in comparison to traditional practices. Possible investors include public authorities, national banks of investments, business angels and relevant farming associations.

2.6 TARGET GROUP 6: EDUCATION/EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Educational institutions will be targeted to promote the technologies used within V4F to younger audiences and help develop the next generation of scientists, innovators and other roles within the renewable energy production and sustainability field.

3. COMMUNICATIONS ACTIVITIES

3.1. COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

A communication toolkit tailored for V4F was developed by EQY at the beginning of the project and made available to all partners on a SharePoint platform. It includes the V4F logo, and logo banner, graphic charter, PowerPoint templates and Word templates.

A poster and a roll-up have also been developed for partners to use for their dissemination activities. Infographics and visuals developed for social media will fit the graphic charter. Other tailored materials could be developed according to the needs of partners (flyers, leaflets, videos, etc.). Materials will be translated in languages facilitating their dissemination to local populations in the demonstration sites and replication sites: Danish, Italian, Flemish, Polish and Icelandic.

Figure 1: Value4Farm logo

Figure 2: Value4Farm Graphic Charter

Figure 3:
PPT
template

Figure 4: Deliverables templates

Figure 5: Value4Farm roll up

3.2. SOCIAL MEDIA

Two social media accounts were created on LinkedIn and X (formerly known as Twitter) at the beginning of the project. Regular communication will be made on these platforms, to create awareness, and to share updates and progress of activities throughout the project duration.

V4F social media accounts are accessible at:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/value4farm>
- X: <https://twitter.com/Value4Farm>

Social media posts will have a general tone, addressed to a non-technical audience. The aim will be to keep the message as simple and accessible as possible for non-specialist audience.

Communication campaigns will focus on:

- General presentation of the project
- Partners presentation
- Work Packages presentation
- Living labs presentation
- Demonstration in the different cities
- Results
- Events attended
- Publications (press releases, newsletters)

V4F partners will have the responsibility to share the posts to their existing network (e-mail, social media, newsletter...), and thus ensuring the messages are conveyed to the relevant stakeholders. Partners will rely on their existing social media networks to share more broadly the project progress.

Table 1: Indicative timetable for main social media campaigns

Date	Topic	Partners involved	Communication support
October – November 2023	General introduction of the project	EQY, INAGRO	Infographics and text
December 2023 – January 2024	Partners presentation	ALL	Infographics and text
March-April 2024	Demonstration sites presentations	EQY, INAGRO, demonstration sites leaders	Photos, infographic and text
End 2024	WP and progress	WP leaders	Photos, infographic and text
Q1 2025	Preliminary result	ALL	Photos, partners quote, infographics and text
Autumn 2025	Demonstration sites progress	Demonstration sites leaders	Photos, partners quote, infographics and text
Q1 2026	Replications status	Replication sites leaders	Infographics and text
Q2 2026	Project results	ALL	Photos, videos, infographics, partners quote/interviews, text

3.3. WEBSITE

The website will be the main channel of communication for 4F. It will feature information on the project activities, objectives, partners, Living Labs, and networking.

The project domain is <https://value4farm.eu/>

The website is available since M6 in February 2024 and will be updated throughout the project. It will be available in English, French, Dutch, Italian, Danish, Icelandic, German and Croatian. The website was developed by EQY and with the support of all partners, to be as appealing, and user friendly as possible. It highlights the Demonstration sites and replication sites of Value4Farm.

Sustainable renewable energy value chains for answering farmers' needs

Explore the future of sustainable agriculture with Value4Farm! We're a collaborative initiative funded by the EU Horizon Europe program, dedicated to integrating renewable energy into farming. Our mission is to increase on-farm renewable energy production while preserving food production, soil health, biodiversity, and reducing water and fertilizer usage! [Join us on the journey to a more sustainable and energy-efficient agricultural future!](#)

DISCOVER PROJECT DETAILS

Figure 6: Mock-up version of the Value4Farm website

3.4. NEWSLETTERS

Several newsletters will be published throughout the project, with the aim to update about the project progress to a different audience from the one reached through social media. The link for newsletter subscription has already been shared to local population of the demonstration sites and will be shared through the partners network by email, thus reaching more industrials and research stakeholders.

The newsletter subscription link was created at the same time as the website through MailChimp. The link will also be published on social media and will be sent by partners to their network. To reach a wider audience through these newsletters, V4F partners will disseminate the news of the project through their existing newsletters.

3.5. WIDE AUDIENCE SCIENCE ARTICLES AND PRESS RELEASES

Articles aiming to reach a general audience will be published throughout the project, to make project activities and goals understandable to a non-specialist and non-scientific audience. Such articles will address e.g. the basic knowledge about biogas, agrivoltaism, crops, legislation and its benefit for the sector compared to traditional agricultural processes. All partners will be invited to contribute to these articles, based on their knowledge, expertise and activities in the project.

Press releases will also be published when achieving significant milestones, notably project results and site visits, to inform target audiences and the general public through relevant media outlets. WBA will build a database of key publications and engage with individual journalists to secure coverage throughout the duration of the project. If appropriate, journalists will be invited to participate in site visits and public workshops, notably for the end-of-project conference.

3.6. VIDEOS

An animated video will be created by EQY to present the project. Lasting between 2 and 4 minutes, in English with subtitles available in relevant languages, it will describe the project and the activities that will be demonstrated in the partners' sites.

4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

All partners will be involved in dissemination activities with a special focus on farmers to generate understanding and to create a favourable environment for the development of agricultural protocols and energy production solutions. Dissemination activities will be developed with a strong result-orientated approach, aiming to deliver relevant formats and contents for each target group in order to achieve maximum impact.

4.1. TARGET GROUPS

These are listed in section 2 of this Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan

4.2. MEANS AND TOOLS OF DISSEMINATION

4.2.1. *Scientific and technical publications*

Partners will publish at least 12 publications in the course of the project as listed in the table below. Reports and results will be published in peer-reviewed journals and magazines according to the IPR protection strategy and the open-access objective. The aim is to disseminate "as open as possible, as close as necessary". The publication content will be decided in conformity with the IP strategy, confidentiality and provisions set out in the consortium agreement. The publishers will be selected among those which both respect the authors'

interests and accept gold access publication and with the biggest impact. Results will also listed, with links, on the V4F website, as well as the partners' and the project newsletters.

Table 2: Scientific publications objectives

Partner	Topic	Peer-reviewed journals targeted
UFZ	Sustainability assessment of the case studies under an integrated life cycle assessment approach (at least two publications)	Journal of Industrial Ecology, Journal of Cleaner Production, Waste Management & Research Energy, Sustainability and Society
AU	Total energy production per land unit, agroecological indicators such as soil quality, GHG emissions, pesticide use, biodiversity, nutrient balances (at least three publications)	Journal of Cleaner Production, Bioresources, Technology Reports, European Journal of Agronomy, Biomass and Bioenergy, Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment
IUNG	Opportunities and barriers for biogas production in Poland and Eastern Europe. Actor-based biogas value chain development. Environmental and aspects of digestate application (at least two publications)	Agriculture, Energies
EIHP	Design of business models for the renewable-based value chains and their sustainable impact (at least two publications)	EGE (Energy, Economy, Ecology and Ethics), Highlights of Sustainability
UCSC / REM / CIB	From small to large agrivoltaics installation in biogas farms, insights from an optimisation scenario studies to off-grid biomethane production and solve the energy-food dilemma (at least one publication)	Applied Energy, Biomass and Bioenergy, Global Change Biology and Bioenergy, Science of Total Environment
UCSC / CIB	Double-cropping rotation reduces of 100% the use of mineral fertilisers with digestate and N-fixing crops (at least one publication)	PNAS, Advances in agronomy, Field crops research, European Journal of Agronomy
UCSC / CIB	Making operational the biogas 4.0 model: improved yield and soil carbon credits generation by enriching crop rotation and integrating conservation tillage with 4.0 digestate use (at least one publication)	PNAS, Advances in agronomy, Field crops research, European Journal of Agronomy

This represents a minimum of 12 scientific publications issued over the course of the project, with an aim of achieving between 30-50 downloads per scientific publications as an indicator of good impact.

4.2.2. Conferences and events

A number of dissemination events will take place during the project implementation to present the progress and results of the project as well as the renewable energy technologies across all target groups.

Each partner will participate in at least one local or European event, fair and/or scientific conferences, workshops, seminars and teleconferences on bioenergy, agrivoltaism, crop systems and biomass production, agricultural developments in waste and land management. One-day events will be organised yearly in different EU regions.

The consortium will organise at least two webinars and at least one one-day event per year in different EU regions, focussing on scientific advances within the project, as well as replication strategy beyond the project's lifetime and future expectations/exploitation activities.

Some conferences will be organised in partnership with CTCN, the implementation arm of the technology mechanism of the UNFCCC and hosted by UNEP. The results of the research will be given a prominent space in the annual World Biogas Summit and Expo organised by WBA – an event that brings together operators, developers, investors, policy makers and academics from around the world to provide thought-leadership and showcase innovation in the global anaerobic digestion and biogas sector. WBA will provide the consortium with a stand, as well as a speaking slot alongside other industry experts.

Additionally, the project results will be presented to the WBA National Association Roundtable, which brings together representatives from biogas trade associations from around the world. The project will be also presented at some external events, for example those organised or attended by EIP-AGRI or FarmEurope.

A table of the events currently identified among partners as platforms to present the VAF project to target groups is provided in Annex 1. This table will be continuously updated.

4.2.3. Networking, knowledge sharing and joint activities

In addition to this programme of events, whenever suitable, workshops and exhibiting will be organised jointly with other EU projects in the areas of bioenergy production, agrivoltaism and crop production. They will be used for technical developments or broader information relative to e.g. LCA, public acceptance, and commercial potential of the solutions.

These events, which will be listed in the plan as they are identified, will enable V4F to establish a strong connection with other projects funded under the Horizon-CL5-2022-D3-02 call and other relevant initiatives and to order to create synergies and a pool of information, particularly through webinars organised by WBA. Also,

partners will contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to joint information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions.

The following research projects that consortium partners are involved have been identified to date for engagement:

- [SUSTRACK](#) - Supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems 2022-2025
- [CARINA](#): boosting the sustainable diversification in agricultural production systems
- [GRANULAR](#): generating new datasets, tools and methods to better understand rural areas
- [SYMOBIO](#): systemic monitoring and modelling of the German bioeconomy
- [BIOGAS-MAMBO](#): looking into biogas upgrading
- [ENERPEDIA](#): looking into renewable energy use in agriculture
- [ALFA](#): looking to encourage take up of biogas in livestock farming
- [CEE2ACT](#): Project related to circular bioeconomy policy
- [BIOECO-UP](#): Bioeconomy value chains
- [ENERFIRST](#) : Plug Energy Efficiency First In
- [USES4HEAT](#): District heating, industrial waste heat, renewable integration, sector coupling, intelligent energy management
- RIBES: Bioeconomy business models in regions
- [CEESU-DIGIT](#): New type of regional energy and climate plans (ECAP)
- [MAESTRI-CE](#): Smart Management and Green Financing for Buildings in Central Europe
- [BIOLOC](#): social innovation and inclusion to accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy in 12 European regions

4.2.4. Other dissemination activities

The farming community will be reached via the farmers network created by the demonstration sites (INA, AU, UCSC, REM, CIB) in WP1, T.1, and be informed via farm visits and open-house events hosted by the demonstrators INA, AU, and UCSC. WBA will also ensure wider dissemination across the EU, with emphasis placed on regions where the potential for renewable energy production is least exploited.

Farmers will also be provided with info sheets and a Decision Support Tool (DST) through training sessions delivered by demonstration and replication partners with the support of WBA, with a focus on parts of the value chain adapted to local needs. It is anticipated to host site visits at demonstration sites: Italy, Belgium, Denmark from October 2024 (M14) and visits to replication sites in 2026.

Policy makers will be specifically reached via the policy briefs developed by UFZ in WP4, T4.4. This task consists of providing a deep analysis of the legislation in the demonstration and replication countries and develop relevant policy recommendations and is due for completion by December 2026.

5. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

Exploitation activities aim to foster the market uptake of the project solutions, and the use of the results to foster the implementation of renewable energy on farms. The first draft of an exploitation plan targeting optimised valorisation of each PR, executed through exploitation activities laid out as T6.4 under the leadership of WBA and the contribution from all partners, is given below. The exploitation plan will include:

- 1) The collection of information on the PRs from all partners of the project
- 2) The identification of strategies to ensure the market uptake of the different PRs
- 3) The development of a roadmap to higher TRL, MRL and SRL,
- 4) The creation, coordinated by WBA, in close collaboration with all the partners, of a Technology Providers board and an End-Users board of at least 10 and 20 members respectively, with at least one from each identified key exploitation sectors (KES) shown in Table 4 below. These members will be solicited for guiding the development of V4F and providing feedback and new ideas for the next step in achieving the exploitation plan objectives.

5.1. EXPLOITATION MEASURES AND STRATEGIES FOR MARKET UPTAKE OF V4F PRs

V4F partners have listed in the table below specific exploitation measures for each of the PRs, providing first elements to the exploitation plan and ensuring the future uptake of the V4F concepts and outcomes.

Table 3: Exploitation measures and strategies for market uptake of V4F PRs

<p>PR1 – Sustainable agricultural crop protocol for the Atlantic pedoclimatic region; PR2 – Sustainable agricultural crop protocol for the Mediterranean pedoclimatic region; PR3 – Protocol of good practices for handling already existing residual crop streams and usage of digestate</p>
<p><u>Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR1/PR2/PR3 into their impacts:</u> The developed protocols are adapted to specific pedoclimatic contexts and are intended to cope with climate change by enabling the reduction of the use of pesticides and mineral fertilisers and the increase of water infiltration capacity, soil organic matter etc. The protocols will be replicated in the relevant regions, through the farms involved in the replication activities and more widely thanks to dissemination activities.</p>
<p><u>Business strategy and competitive advantage:</u> The protocols present advantages to be adaptable to a wide range of renewable energy technologies (e.g.</p>

anaerobic digestion, agrivoltaism, green biorefineries). For the crop protocols developed by AU and UCSC (PR1/PR2), the nitrogen autonomy from inclusion of N-fixing crops and the recycling of residues and cover crops through biogas allows a reduction in the use of mineral fertilisers.

Associated management of intellectual property:

The protocols will be published in open access and disseminated locally for farmers

PR4 – High-efficiency flameless microturbines

Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR4 into its impacts:

The business models elaborated in T5.1 will facilitate the market uptake of the micro-20 microturbine, and the ORC loop. Particularly, a market study will be carried out in order to better target the needs of users and then adapt the market strategy. Partnerships will be created, including through the Technology Providers board.

Business strategy and competitive advantage:

The micro-20 microturbine developed by MITIS presents several competitive advantages, including its low emission flameless combustion, its low maintenance requirements, its high efficiency for small-scale (bio)gas-based power generation, and the user-friendliness of the plug-and-play system. The ORC system can be used as a bottoming cycle to the micro-20 microturbine to further improve the electrical efficiency and therefore increase the return on investment of the installed system. The ORC will also be exploited as a standalone product to improve electrical yield of large internal combustion engine biogas systems through waste heat recovery conversion.

Associated management of intellectual property:

The IP developed in the project will be owned and protected by MITIS through patenting if pertinent. The results of the demonstrations will be published in open access to maximise their conversion into impacts

PR5 – Path for maximising food and energy output for large-scale farms

Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR5 into its impacts:

This demonstrated value chain targets relatively large-scale farms as are common in Denmark (>100ha). The exploitation will firstly be through a few Danish replication farms (ca.5). This will be supported by the setting-up of “open-house” arrangements for farmers, farmers cooperatives and farm advisors, which usually are very well attended in Denmark. The dissemination or arrangements and results will involve Food and BioCluster Denmark, which has an extensive business network operating. In any case, the demonstrated value chain will be assessed in terms of economic benefits and an associated business model will be created.

Business strategy and competitive advantage:

This path can be fully or partially appropriated by the targeted farms and industries. Validation of results are done in peer-reviewed journals.

Associated management of intellectual property:

The results of the demonstration of the value chain will be published in open access to maximise its exploitation.

PR6 – Simple path to mobility for small-scale farms

Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR6 into its impacts:

The demonstrated value chain will be assessed in terms of economic benefits and associated business models will be created. Once optimised, the value chain will be replicated in Iceland in the frame of the project.

Business strategy and competitive advantage:

The value chain targets small-scale farms, which often do not have the capacity to equip themselves with biogas units, as the market is still oriented towards large-scale biogas plants. Using the produced energy for mobility fits perfectly with the requirements on the farms.

Associated management of intellectual property:

The results of the demonstration of the value chain will be published in open access to maximise its exploitation.

PR7 – Efficient off-grid biomethane plant

Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR7 into its impacts:

The value chain coupling agrivoltaic panels with biomethane plants will be presented for further implementation in several farms in Italy (CIB) and Denmark (AU). The results will also be presented to the technology providers board.

Business strategy and competitive advantage:

This innovative value chain presents the advantage of enabling off-grid functioning of a biomethane plant, as the biogas upgrading is an energy greedy process.

Associated management of intellectual property:

The results of the study will be published in open access to maximise the exploitation.

PR8 – Open-access decision support tool (DST)

Specific exploitation measures taken to facilitate the transfer of PR8 into its impacts:

The DST will be widely disseminated among farmers, and will benefit from a concrete application in replication activities.

Business strategy and competitive advantage:

The DST will provide at the same time information on farming practices and on the possibilities of renewable-based solutions that can be implemented. This multi-factor, multi-criteria tool will allow farmers to make the best choices adapted to their needs.

Associated management of intellectual property:

Online open-access.

5.2. DEVELOPMENT OF A ROADMAP TO HIGHER TRL, MRL AND SRL

5.2.1. Path leading to exploitation

Based on the validated methodology of the EIT InnoEnergy, the V4F partners will assess and improve the different scales of readiness levels along the project lifetime, all relevant for exploitation: Technology Readiness Level (TRL), through the technological developments of the project, Market Readiness Level (MRL), Societal Readiness Level (SRL) in task T6.4, summarised in Table 4 below, which shows what has already been validated at the start of the project (blue cells) and what will be during the project (green cells).

Table 4: Path towards TRL9, MRL10 and SRL5

TRL (from 1 to 9)	MRL (from 1 to 10)	SRL (from 1 to 5)
1. Fundamental research	1. Unsatisfied needs identified	1. Recognition of the stakeholders
2. Applied research	2. Identification of the potential business opportunities	2. Identification of the expectations, interests and concerns of stakeholders
3. Research to prove feasibility	3. System analysis and general environment	
4. Laboratory demonstration	4. Market research	
5. Validation in a relevant environment	5. Targeting	3. Recognition of possible types of conflicts
6. Field demonstration of whole system	6. Industry analysis	4. Understanding national and local factors and critical issues
7. Industrial prototype	7. Competitor analysis and positioning	
8. Product industrialisation	8. Value proposition	
9. Market certification and sales authorisation	9. Product/service definition	5. Involvement of stakeholders
	10. Business model	

5.2.2. Path to commercialisation and roadmap to higher TRL, MRL, SRL

At the end of the V4F project, the partners will keep implementing several actions, especially the market uptake of the renewable energy technologies developed by MITIS, and the ownership and improvement of the agricultural protocols by farmers. Business schemes and agreements will be designed for specific and general

purposes to this aim in WP5 task T5.1. V4F will decide on the different exploitation routes as identified in the exploitation plan fully designed under WP6 task T6.1 and will start the funding research to implement this path.

Private and public R&I funding will be considered for these next steps depending on the nature of the PRs and of the partners’ organisations, a follow-up will be done on customers reached.

Partners will continue some activities after the project to go beyond achieved results, by identifying remaining obstacles, requirements and actions involved in reaching higher TRL, MRL and SRL (e.g. Optimisation of the DST, further research on agricultural data, improvement of biogas equipment). The path to reach TRL9, MRL10 and SRL5 will be drafted in a roadmap under WP6 task T6.4.

5.3. CREATION OF TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS AND END-USERS BOARDS

WBA, in close collaboration with all the partners, will coordinate the creation of a Technology Providers Board gathering start-up and industries, and of an End-Users Board gathering mostly farmers and advisors. The boards will assemble a minimum of 10 and 20 members respectively with at least one from each identified key exploitation sectors (KES) shown in Table 5 below. These members will be solicited for guiding the development of V4F and providing feedback and new ideas for the next step in achieving the exploitation plan objectives.

Calls for board members have already been placed via T1.1 and all partners will be asked to share notices across their own communication networks. The first list of board members is due at M12 (August 2024).

Table 5: Key exploitation sectors

Boards	Key Exploitation Sectors
Technology Providers	Scientific Community: researchers on bioenergy generation, agrivoltaics, (organic) crops
	Manufacturers of biogas and agrivoltaic/photovoltaic plants, electricity and gas distribution networks
End-Users	Farm end-users, cooperatives
	Agricultural associations at national and local levels
	Policy makers, energy and food agencies

The objective of the boards will be to enlarge the knowledge sharing and to ensure the replication of the project’s demonstrated solutions. It will pave the way for the uptake of the solutions in the different sectors.

Regular meetings will be held with the members of the boards to present the progress of the project in order to consolidate links with potential end-users and ensure uptake of solutions. They will in particular be invited to

attend the V4F final workshop. The board members will be associated to visits and events held in the demonstration sites facilities.

6. NETWORK/STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS

To support the effective deployment of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, a network analysis and stakeholder mapping is being conducted among partners, leading to the development of a database to be used by different project partners for their engagement activities. Partners are also invited to provide details of their broader network and in-house publications, such as Biogas Informa for CIB, who also communicate to over 1,000 members, 800 of which are agricultural companies with biogas and/or biomethane systems, with the others plant construction companies or other companies and bodies connected to the sector.

A preliminary list of relevant V4F organisations that partners are already engaging with is provided in Annex 2 and will be continuously updated.

7. MONITORING/KPIS

Below is the list of KPIs identified as representative of the success level in executing the DEC plan. Progress towards achieving those KPIs will be monitored through a tracking spreadsheet to be completed by each partner with remedial action taken as necessary to correct any under-achieving activity.

Table 6: KPIs

Category	Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Dissemination	Number of scientific papers submitted	<10	10-15	>15
	Number of downloads per scientific publication	<30	30-50	>50
Communication	Material downloads from the website	<100	100-300	>300

	Relevant contacts made through the website	<15	15-30	>30
	Number of followers on social media at the end of the project	<300	300-500	>500
Dissemination	Number of outreach events organised	<6	6-10	>10
Dissemination	Number of external outreach events attended	<15	15-20	>20
Dissemination	People reached per event	<100	100-300	>300
Dissemination	Number of farmers per training session	<6	6-10	>10
Dissemination	Number of training sessions	<15	15-20	>20
Dissemination	Number of projects and working groups with which collaboration is established	<5	5-15	>15
Communication	Number of popular science articles published	<10	10-15	>15
Communication	Number of readings in total	<500	500-1,000	>1,000
Communication	Web page visits per year	<3,000	3,000-5,000	>5,000

Communication	Number of posts on social media per year	<20	20-30	>30
Communication	Number of views on social media per post	<500	500-1,000	>1,00
Communication	Paper or digital brochure/leaflet distribution	<500	500-1,000	>1,000
Communication	Number of views of the video	<2,000	2,000-3,000	>3,000
Communication	Number of communication campaigns organised	< 5	5-10	>10

8. BARRIERS/MITIGATION

Through its deployment, the V4F pathway towards outcomes and impacts could be hampered by a number of barriers. When it comes to Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, the partners have identified the following potential barriers and laid out the mitigation measures taken.

8.1. REGIONAL LANGUAGES

Ten local languages are represented by the 14 partners (Croatian, Danish, Dutch, English, French, German, Icelandic, Italian, Polish) and DEC activities are likely to reach out to other communities using a different regional language. Whilst the partners will use English among themselves as the common language during the project, regional language barriers could create misunderstanding in sharing knowledge with external stakeholders and encouraging uptake of the V4F solutions.

As a result, the consortium will endeavour to translate all external communications into the local language of the targeted audience and ensure a native speaker among the partners engaging with that audience. This will be particularly critical around the engagement with the Technology Providers and End-Users boards.

8.2. TECHNICAL LANGUAGE

Certain aspects of the project tasks are of a highly technical nature and the partners shouldn't therefore assume that all stakeholders – including fellow consortium partners – will be familiar with the technical jargon or academic concepts used by researchers and academics or other partners in other contexts. To avoid any misunderstanding, it is therefore critical that all acronyms or concepts specific to a certain discipline are explained – either as a separate glossary or within the document shared with other stakeholders.

Also, partners must ensure that communications activities remain accessible to the key audience groups and the general public. This might involve putting documents to the test but submitting them to representatives of those groups prior to publication for feedback and adaptation.

8.3. POLITICAL CLIMATE

Both at EU and member state levels, reducing the carbon footprint of agriculture is of high importance, and in line with the EU Green Deal. However, the transition to more sustainable agricultural value chains has recently been met with protests from farmers across Europe due to the cost and administrative burden of implementing the measures requested by the EU and national governments. This could impact on the uptake of the V4F solutions and exploitation objectives.

It is therefore necessary to ensure that the transition is supported by EU and national governments (e.g. through financial incentives) by interacting with policy makers from the onset and disseminating the benefits of the value chains among them. Moreover, researchers will be continuously reflecting on how scientific insights can be used to reach political goals related to the reduction of the agricultural carbon footprint.

8.4. ECONOMIC CONTEXT

The current high cost of energy is an opportunity for farmers to shift the current energy production and use paradigm on their farms and increase the profitability of renewable solutions to have on site. However, the proposed solutions must be integrated in a whole value chain which is a big shift and the investment needed is usually very high. The rise of interest rates and inflation can hamper the investments in such a transition and impact on end-users' readiness to take up the V4F solutions.

Whilst partners in WP1, WP4 and WP5 will actively engage with farmers, provide detailed economic assessments and establish market positioning/develop business cases respectively, WP6 will be mindful of presenting the medium- and long-term economic benefits of embracing V4F outcomes throughout dissemination activities to facilitate exploitation.

8.5. SOCIAL AND SOCIETAL CONTEXT

Farmers are increasingly encouraged to adopt more sustainable practices. However, they may be reluctant to rapidly shift their established practices towards the establishment of new value chains and may show a lack of confidence in them – impacting on exploitation goals.

To provide reassurance and win hearts and minds, farmers will be involved throughout the project through partners' networks, the End Users board and targeted dissemination which will aim to overcome this barrier.

8.6. LEGAL AND REGULATORY CONTEXT

Regulations and EU strategic goals, mirrored in the EU Green Deal, aim to reduce reliance of agriculture on fossil fuels, encouraging farmers to act as prosumers of renewable energy. There is however a lack of legislations/regulations and guidelines at national level across EU that would encourage farmers to effectively implement renewable energy technologies on their farms. There are also significant differences from countries to countries and the legislative framework explored in D1. - Regulation framework analysis led by UFZ for the three demonstration countries (Belgium Denmark, Italy) to identify good practices and obstacles to the implementation of innovative concepts - should help address those issues.

Dissemination activities will focus on engaging with policymakers whilst WP1 and WP4 will monitor the regulatory frameworks to ensure appropriate guidance is provided to farmers towards implementation of the solutions.

8.7. PRACTICAL BARRIERS TO DEC PLAN DEPLOYMENT

In addition to language and broader contextual barriers, there are a few practical aspects to the delivery of the DEC plan that might hamper its success:

- Funding issues: (e.g.: Cost of organising events/site visits going over budget (including travel/accommodation costs for board members)
Good planning, regular status updates and planning of resources/activities reallocation among partners will be implemented to minimise any risk of budget deviation across the project.
- Health and Safety issues (e.g.: Site visits not possible due to H&S issues at the site)
Concerned partners will be trained and briefed by technology providers and equipment providers in order to have all the information necessary to conduct a safe and smooth demonstration.
- Lack of engagement from board members e.g. Unable to attend meetings due to other commitments and provide timely feedback

The involvement of all partners in engaging with the Technology Providers and End Users boards can ensure that a board member becoming unable to sustain the commitment to the project can be replaced and that the breadth of feedback across the membership can reduce the risk of key information being

lacking. Additionally, it is proposed that board members be provided with Terms of Reference at the time of joining so that they appreciate fully the commitment they make to the project when signing up.

- Not enough targets gathered for good exploitation: All partners being involved in the WP6 makes the risk low. The DEC plan will be re-evaluated if needed during the project, whilst the involvement of Technical Providers and End-user Boards will ensure the good exploitation of the project results.

9. IMPLEMENTATION SCHEDULE

A detailed implementation schedule based on current input from some partners is attached in Annex 3. This table will be continuously updated to reflect additional information and decisions made by the consortium on the most appropriate channels and platforms for dissemination, exploitation and communication.

10. ANNEX 1 – EVENTS IDENTIFIED FOR V4F PROMOTION @29 FEBRUARY 2024

Partner	Event	Type	Location	Date	Attend	Target audience
2024						
WBA/ UKREAD	Low Carbon Agriculture Show	Expo	Stoneleigh, UK	6-7 March	y (WBA)	Farmers Technology providers
INA	ManuREsource	Conf	Antwerp, Belgium	21-22 March	y	Farm Advisors, Industry
WBA	IFAT 2024	Conf/Expo	Munich, Germany	13-17 May	?	Water, waste management
INA	REGATEC	Conf	Lund, Sweden	15-16 May	? (online)	Renewable energy
UKREAD	Renewable Energy Revenues Summit 2024	Conf	London, UK	22-23 May	?	Investors
EIHP	AGRO-ARCA	Expo	TBC, Croatia	May	?	Farmers, technology providers
EIHP	AGrores	Symp	Trebinje, Croatia	27-30 May		Farmers, technology providers, academics
INA	18th IWA World Conference on Anaerobic Digestion	Conf	Istanbul, Turkey	2-6 June	?	Wastewater treatment anaerobic digestion
UKREAD	UK Solar Summit	Conf	London, UK	4-5 June	x	Solar
UKREAD	Word Conference Agrivoltaics		Denver, USA	11-13 June	x	Agrivoltaics
UKREAD	Large Scale Solar Southern Europe		Athens, Greece	2-3 July	x	Solar
UFZ	Life Cycle Innovation Conference	Conf	Berlin, Germany	5-7 July	y	Scientists, researchers, academics
WBA	World Biogas Summit/Expo	Conf/Expo	Birmingham, UK	10-11 July	y	Biogas, Policy makers Technology providers
EIHP	Agro-Rocks	Conf	TBC, Croatia	Sept/Oct	?	Farmers, technology providers

WBA	RWM	Expo	Birmingham, UK	11-12 Sept	y	Waste management, anaerobic digestion
EIHP	ISDTA	Symp	TBC, Croatia	November		Digital technology in agriculture
CIB/ WBA	Ecomondo 2024	Expo	Rimini, Italy	5-8 November	y	Renewable energy, recycling, waste management
UKREAD	3rd Annual AgriVoltaics Europe		Vienna, Austria	5-7 November	?	Agrioltaics
2025						
EIHP	60th Croatian & 20th International Symposium on Agriculture	Symp	Dubrovnik, Croatia	February	y	Farmers
EIHP	Balkan Solar Summit	Conf	Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina (tbc)	February	?	Solar
EIHP	AGRO-ARCA	Expo	TBC, Croatia	May	?	Farmers, technology providers
EIHP	Agro-Rocks	Conf	TBC, Croatia	Sept/Oct	?	Farmers, technology providers
UFZ	Life Cycle Management Conference	Conf	Palermo, Italy	TBC	?	Scientists, researchers, academics

Many of these are annual events so the calendar will be expanded over time to reflect opportunities to attend future editions. Events organised by media outlets relevant to the V4F sectors will also be monitored for potential engagement in the course of the project.

11. ANNEX 2 – STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING @29 FEBRUARY 2024

This table will be continuously updated to reflect additional information provided by partners in the course of the project.

Organisation	Sector	Partner	Location
Farm Europe	Agriculture	INA	
Biogas-E	Biogas	INA	Belgium
Denuo	Biogas/Recycling	INA	Belgium
Vlaco	Digestate Use /Composting	INA	Belgium
VEKA	Policy	INA	Belgium
Boerenbond	Agriculture	INA	Belgium
Forrest Hills Solar Farm	Solar/Academia	UKREAD	UK
NFU Energy	Agriculture	UKREAD	UK
European MEPs	Policy	WBA	Belgium
European Bioeconomy Bureau	Bioeconomy/Policy	WBA	Belgium
European Environmental Bureau	Environment	WBA	Belgium
Brilian	Circular Economy	WBA	Belgium
COPECO-GECA	Agriculture	WBA	
IFOAM	Agriculture	WBA	
European Biogas Association	Biogas	WBA	
Danish Biogas Association	Biogas	WBA	Denmark
University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture	Agriculture	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Chamber of Agriculture	Agriculture	EIHP	Croatia
Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences - Osijek	Agrobiotechnology	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Ministry of Agriculture	Agriculture/Policy	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development	Sustainability/Policy	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Paying Agency for Agriculture, Fisheries, and Rural Development	Agriculture/Finance	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Agency for Agriculture and Food	Agriculture/Policy	EIHP	Croatia
Croatian Innovation and Development Agencies: REDEA, PORA, DUNEA, ZADRA NOVA JURA, RA KAZUP, RRA ŠIBENIK REGEA , CEKOM VINKOVCI; MENE; RA VSZ	Research/Finance	EIHP	Croatia

Bioeconomy e.V	Bioeconomy	UFZ	Germany
German Biomass Research Centre, DBFZ	Biomass/Research	UFZ	Germany

12. ANNEX 3 – IMPLEMENTATION SCHEDULE @29 FEBRUARY 2024

Lead Partner (s)	Description	Due date	Delivered
WBA	KOM press release + translations (D6.2)	Asap after KOM	Nov 2023
2024			
WBA	DEC plan (D6.1)	29 Feb 2024 (M6)	
EQY	Website launch (D6.2)	Feb 2024 (M6)	
UKREAD/EQY/ WBA	Press release upon delivery of farmers' needs report (D1.1) and other WP1 deliverables as appropriate (D6.2)	Mar 2024 (M7)	
AU/UCSC/ WBA	Articles (or scientific paper?) about development of agricultural protocols (D2.3/D2.4) (D6.3)	Jun 2024 (M10)	
WBA	Stand and dissemination at World Biogas Expo (D6.3)	10-11 Jul 2024	
MITIS/ WBA	Article (or scientific paper?) on micro 20 turbine design (D2.1 /D6.3)	Jul 2024 (M11)	
WBA	First List of Technology Providers and End-Users Boards published (D6.4)	Aug 2024 (M12)	
EQY	Newsletter 1 (D6.3)	Aug 2024 (M12)	
WBA	Presentation of the project to Autumn National Associations Roundtable (D6.3)	Autumn 2024 (M14-15)	
REM/CIB/UCSC/ AU/ INA/WBA	Potential demonstration site visit (Italy to coincide with Ecomondo?) (D6.3)	Nov 2024 (M15)	
EQY	Press release on overall project progress (D6.2)	Autumn 2024 (M14-15)	
WBA/ALL	First Technology Providers Board meeting at Ecomondo (5-8 Nov 2024) (D6.4)	Nov 2024 (M15)	
2025			
ALL	Attendance at events as per separate table (D6.2/D6.3)	Throughout 2025 (M17-28)	
WBA/ALL	Technology Providers Board Meeting (D6.4)	Spring 2025 (M19-20)	
INA/AU/REM CIB/UCSC/WBA	Potential demonstration site visit (Belgium?) with Technology Providers Board invited (D6.3)	Spring 2025 (M19-20)	
EQY	Press release on overall project progress (D6.2)	Spring 2025 (M19-20)	
WBA	Presentation of the project to Spring National Associations Roundtable (D6.3)	Spring 2025 (M19-20)	

MITIS/ WBA	Article (or scientific paper?) on micro 20 turbine design (D2.2 /D6.3)	Aug 2025 (M24)	
EQY	Newsletter 2 (D6.2)	Aug 2025 (M24)	
WBA/ALL	Technology Providers Board Meeting (D6.4)	Autumn 2025 (M25-26)	
WBA	Presentation of the project to Autumn National Associations Roundtable (D6.3)	Autumn 2025 (M25-26)	
EIHP/EQY/WBA/ EQY	Press releases / media articles on replication sites progress (D6.2)	Between Sep 2025 and Feb 2027 (M24-42)	
2026			
ALL	Attendance at events as per separate table (D6.3)	Throughout 2026 (M29-40)	
WBA	Presentation of the project to Spring National Associations Roundtable (D6.3)	Spring 2026 (M31-32)	
EQY	Press release on overall project progress (D6.2)	Spring 2026 (M31-32)	
EQY	Newsletter 3 (D6.2)	August 2026 (M36)	
WBA	Presentation of the project to Autumn National Associations Roundtable (D6.3)	Autumn 2026 (M37-38)	
AU/INA/REM CIB/UCSC/WBA	Potential demonstration site visits (Belgium/Denmark/Italy) with Technology Providers and End-Users Boards invited (D3.1/2/3 – D6.4)	Dec 2026 (M40) or Jan 2027 (M41)	
AU/INA/REM CIB/UCSC/EQY/ WBA	Press release (or scientific paper?) about visits to demonstration sites and optimised value chains (D6.3)	Dec 2026 (M40)	
UFZ/UKREAD/ WBA	Press releases about sustainability analysis of the value chains (D4.1) and policy recommendations (D4.2) (D6.3)	Dec 2026 (M40)	
UFZ/UKREAD/E QY WBA	Press release/articles on Open Access Decision Support Tool (DST) – (D4.3) (D6.2/3)	Between Dec 2026 (M40) and Feb 2027 (M42)	
2027			
WBA/EQY	Press release about roadmap for further exploitation (D6.2)	Jan 2027 (M41)	
WBA	End of project workshop (D6.3)	Jan 2027 (M41)	
EQY/WBA	Press release/articles about overall project outcomes (D6.2)	Feb 2027 (M42)	
EQY/WBA	Newsletter 4 (D6.2)	Feb2027 (M42)	

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